

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

Evaluation Report (acceptance note) for **TEBT-2024-0002**

Submission information table

Submission Title	Reporting Quality of Systematic Review Protocols in Environmental and Occupational Toxicology: A meta-epidemiology study protocol
Submission Reference	TEBT-2024-0002
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley
Number of Reviewers	2
Submission Type	Method (Protocol for Planned Study) ▾
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10795519
Evaluation Stage	Acceptance Note ▾
Evaluation Date	11 Dec 2024
Recommendation	Accept ▾

Acceptance note

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

This manuscript has been **accepted** for publication by the handling editor Paul Whaley after 3 rounds of revision in response to 1 round of editorial triage and 2 rounds of peer-review.

In the editor's opinion, this protocol is either a [Category 04 or Category 03 preregistration](#) (the data already exists and some of it may already have been accessed as part of the piloting process). According to our **Registered Reports** policy, the manuscript following from this protocol will be accepted so long as the researchers reasonably adhere to their planned methods.

During triage, the handling editor recommended restructuring and adding detail to the described methods, in order to make best use of the peer-review process. During peer-review, most comments related to improving the conciseness and impact of the protocol. Some comments related to further developing the coding strategy to ensure the authors will gather the data they need in order to deliver their study goals, and to providing a more detailed analysis plan for this data.

Insights from the evaluation process include: reinforcement of the importance of being clear that PRISMA is a reporting checklist and not guidance for the conduct of systematic reviews; the value of piloting planned methods, which the authors did in detail; and the importance of continuing discussion about exclusionary practices in the planning of research.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10942477>